

SULPHINATION. PART I. SULPHINATION OF SOME 7-HYDROXYCOUMARIN DERIVATIVES

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The action of thionyl chloride on some 7-hydroxycoumarin derivatives in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride has been studied. The reaction has led to the formation of sulphinic acids of the coumarin derivatives.

The action of thionyl chloride on phenols, phenolic ethers and aromatic hydrocarbons in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride has been studied by various workers (Colby and McLoughlin, *Ber.*, 1887, 20, 195; Parker, *ibid.*, 1890, 23, 1884; Michaelis and Loth, *ibid.*, 1894, 27, 2540; Smiles *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 696; 1907, 91, 1118; 1908, 93, 735; 1910, 97, 2248) furnishing either sulphoxide (A) or trisulphonium compound (B), depending upon the conditions used.

There is only one instance in literature, that is of *m*-5-xyleneol methyl ether, where together with sulphoxide a small quantity of sulphinic acid is also formed (Smiles and Rossignol, *Ber.*, 1908, 93, 745).

In the present investigation, this reaction has been applied to 7-hydroxy-4-methyl-, 7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethyl- and 7-hydroxy-6 ethyl-4-methyl-coumarins, yielding the respective sulphinic acids (IA), (IB) and (IC) in good yields. They were characterised by preparing ammonium salt and S-benzylisothiurea derivatives.

[A: R=H; R'=H. B: R=H; R'=Me. C: R=Et; R'=H].

The constitution of these sulphinic acids follows from the fact, that they exhibit coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, indicating -SO₂H group to be in position *ortho* to OH group. In the case of the first two coumarin derivatives, both the positions *ortho* to OH, viz., 6 and 8, are available for the reaction, but

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the sulphinic acids obtained from these coumarin derivatives, on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide, give the respective sulphonic acids which are not the same as the known 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-6-sulphonic acid (IIIA) and 3:4-dimethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-6-sulphonic acid (IIIB), described by Merchant and Shah (this *Journal*, 1947, 34, 35; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 884); hence $-SO_2H$ group must have entered the position '8' of the coumarin derivative, forming (IA) and (IB) respectively. In the case of 4-methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin, position '6' is already blocked and the only position, *ortho* to OH, available for the reaction is '8'. This has been confirmed as the sulphinic acid, obtained from this coumarin, on oxidation with hydrogen peroxide affords the sulphonic acid (IIC), which has been identified by the mixed m.p. of its *S*-benzylisothioureia derivative with that of sulphonic acid (IIC), prepared according to Merchant and Shah (*loc. cit.*).

The isolation of the sulphinic acids in a pure state presented difficulties due to their unstable nature. In certain cases the product decomposed during crystallisation, and other methods had to be used to obtain sulphinic acids in pure form (vide Experimental). The sulphinic acids are soluble in alcohol, acetone but insoluble in solvents like benzene, ether etc.

The potassium salts of the sulphinic acids, (IA, IB and IC), on refluxing with alcoholic solution of ethyl iodide furnished the respective ethyl sulphones, (IVA, IVB and IVC), and on treating the sulphinic acids with mercuric chloride, the corresponding chloromercuri derivatives, (VA, VB and VC), were obtained, $-SO_2H$ group being replaced by $-HgCl$ radical.

[A : R=H ; R'=H. B : R=H ; R'=Me. C : R=Et ; R'=H].

The formation of the sulphinic acids during the reaction is interesting, and this provides a new and direct method for the synthesis of sulphinic acids of hydroxycoumarin derivatives, which otherwise would have been difficult to obtain. The amount of anhydrous aluminium chloride used in this reaction is three moles to one mole of coumarin as recommended in the Fries and Friedel-Crafts reactions of the coumarin derivatives (Thakor and Shah, this *Journal*, 1946, 22, 199). Thionyl chloride was used in a little excess as poor yields were obtained by using theoretical quantity.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

4-Methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphinic Acid (IA).—Thionyl chloride (6.4 g., 2*M*) was gradually added to an intimate mixture of 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (5 g., 1*M*) and powdered anhydrous AlCl_3 (11.3 g., 3*M*), cooled in ice. The reaction mixture, which turned into a transparent mass, was left overnight at room temperature. Crushed ice and HCl (24 c.c.) were added to the mixture when the milky solution slowly deposited a crystalline solid after scratching the walls of the container and leaving it in a refrigerator overnight. The impure solid was filtered, washed and dried in vacuum. It was then triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution (dilute ammonium hydroxide may also be used) and filtered from the insoluble residue comprising mainly unchanged coumarin and other impurities. The filtrate was made just neutral and any flocculent precipitate separating was removed and to the clear solution more HCl added, scratched and left in the refrigerator. White sulphinic acid slowly separated. It was filtered, washed and dried in vacuum. M.p. varied from $155-65^\circ$ (decomp.), yield 3-4 g. The substance on crystallisation from alcohol melted at a lower temperature than the crude one. The pure sample of sulphinic acid was therefore obtained by acidifying its ammonium salt (*vide infra*), m.p. $175-77^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: S, 13.50. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_5\text{S}$ requires S, 13.33%). It gave a deep purple coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and no fluorescence with alkali.

Ammonium Salt.—Dry ammonia gas was bubbled in ice-cooled solution of the sulphinic acid (IA, 0.5 g.) in absolute alcohol (5 c.c.) till saturation. Ammonium salt separated slowly in a crystalline form. It was crystallised from alcohol containing a few drops of water in shining needles, m.p. $205-207^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.76. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{NS}$ requires N, 5.45%). It is very soluble in water.

S-Benzylisothiourea Derivative.—Potassium salt of the sulphinic acid (IA) was first prepared by adding alcoholic potash dropwise to the alcoholic solution of the sulphinic acid with good stirring till permanent yellow tinge appeared in the solution. The white salt separating was filtered, washed well with alcohol and dried in vacuum.

To the aqueous solution of the potassium salt a saturated aqueous solution of S-benzylisothiourea hydrochloride (Chamber and Watts, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1941, 6, 376) was added at room temperature when a yellowish oil separated which gradually solidified. It crystallised from 25% alcohol, m.p. $121-23^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.89. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2\text{S}_2$ requires N, 6.89%).

The above derivative was also prepared directly by adding dropwise NaOH solution to sulphinic acid, suspended in water, till a yellow tinge appeared in the solution. The yellow tinge was destroyed by adding a little more of sulphinic acid, the excess of which was filtered off, and to the filtrate an aqueous solution of S-benzylisothiourea hydrochloride was added. The product was isolated as before.

4-Methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphonic Acid (IIA): (Sodium salt).—Hydrogen peroxide (3 c.c. of 100 vol. + 7 c.c. of water) was added to the solution of the

above sulphinic acid (0.5 g.) in sodium bicarbonate solution and the reaction was allowed to proceed for about an hour at room temperature and then it was heated on a water-bath for about an hour, cooled, just acidified with HCl, concentrated to a small bulk and poured in a saturated solution of common salt and kept in a refrigerator. The white sodium salt of sulphonic acid which separated was filtered, washed and dried.

S-Benzylisothiourea derivative of (IIA), prepared from the above sodium salt, was crystallised from water containing a few drops of alcohol in shining needles, m.p. 195-97°. (Found: N, 6.95. $C_{18}H_{18}O_6N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.64%). The mixed m.p. with the same derivative of 4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-6-sulphonic acid (IIIA), prepared according to Merchant and Shah (*loc. cit.*), gave a depression of about 25°.

4-Methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-ethylsulphone (IVA).—Ethyl iodide (0.5 c.c.) was added to the solution of potassium salt of sulphinic acid (0.5 g.) in a mixture of water (3 c.c.) and alcohol (4 c.c.) and the mixture was refluxed for about 15 hours. A negligible amount of a solid, m.p. 285° (decomp.) (not investigated), which separated from the boiling mixture, was removed and the solution was cooled when the sulphone slowly separated in quite a pure state. It crystallised from alcohol in white flat needles, m.p. 179-80°. (Found: S, 12.20. $C_{12}H_{12}O_5S$ requires S, 11.94%). It is insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in alcohol.

4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-chloromercuri-coumarin (VA).—An alcoholic solution of mercuric chloride (1 g.) was added to the sulphinic acid (IA, 0.5 g.) in alcohol (5 c.c.) when a crystalline solid slowly separated with continuous evolution of SO_2 . The substance was purified by refluxing first with water and then with alcohol. It did not melt till 270° but became yellowish at 250° and pasty at 270°. (Found: Hg, 49.09. $C_{10}H_7O_3ClHg$ requires Hg, 48.79%). It is insoluble in water and in organic solvents. It dissolves in sodium hydroxide solution with a blue fluorescence.

3:4-Dimethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphinic Acid (IB).—Thionyl chloride (6.4 g.) was added to an intimate mixture of 3:4-dimethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (5 g.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (10 g.) and the reaction was allowed to proceed in the same manner as in case of (IA) and worked up similarly. The sulphinic acid was isolated in nearly pure state by following the same procedure, as before. A large amount of mud-like byproducts was removed during the process. It was dried in vacuum (yield 2.5-3 g., m.p. 164-65°, decomp.). It was crystallised from alcohol in needles, m.p. 169-70° (decomp.). (Found: S, 12.35. $C_{11}H_{10}O_5S$ requires S, 12.6%). It developed a blue coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and no fluorescence with alkali.

Ammonium salt was prepared and crystallised, as before, in shining white prismatic needles, m.p. 205-207° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.52. $C_{11}H_{13}O_5NS$ requires N, 5.16%). It is very soluble in water and insoluble in alcohol and in other solvents. It gives a bluish violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

S-Benzylisothiourea derivative of (IB), prepared as before, was crystallised from rectified spirit in glistening needles, m.p. 185-87° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.69. $C_{18}H_{20}O_5N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.66%).

3:4-Dimethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphonic acid (IIB) was obtained by oxidation of the sulphinic acid in the same way as in (IA) and the sodium salt of sulphonic acid was isolated.

S-Benzylisothiourea derivative of (IIB) was prepared from the sodium salt and crystallised from dilute alcohol in monoclinic needles, m.p. 185-87°. (Found: N, 6.85. $C_{10}H_{20}O_6N_2S_2$ requires N, 6.43%). [The m.p. of S-benzylisothiourea-derivative of 3:4-dimethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin 6-sulphonic acid described by Merchant and Shah (*loc. cit.*) is 224-25°].

3:4-Dimethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-ethylsulphone (IVB) was prepared by refluxing the solution of potassium salt of sulphinic acid (IB, 1 g.) in a mixture of alcohol (8 c.c.), water (6 c.c.) and ethyl iodide (1.5 c.c.) for 15 hours. The sulphone was crystallised from alcohol in shining plates, m.p. 207-208°. (Found: S, 11.67. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 11.34%).

3:4-Dimethyl-7-hydroxy-8-chloromercuri-coumarin (VB) was prepared by adding an alcoholic solution of $HgCl_2$ to an alcoholic solution of sulphinic acid (IB) and was purified as in the case of (VA) in shining needles. It did not melt till 270° but became pasty at this temperature. (Found: Hg, 47.6. $C_{11}H_8O_2ClHg$ requires Hg, 47.2%).

4-Methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphinic Acid (IC).—Thionyl chloride (3.7 c.c.) was added to the intimate mixture of 4-methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (5 g.) and powdered anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (10 g.) and the reaction was allowed to proceed as in the previous case. The product was worked up similarly, m.p. 160° (decomp.), yield 3-4 g.

This sulphinic acid was found to form insoluble sodium or ammonium salt when treated with sodium bicarbonate or ammonia solution. So the residue obtained after treatment of the crude product with sodium bicarbonate solution was heated to boiling with water and filtered immediately. From the filtrate by acidification with HCl, a good amount of the sulphinic acid was recovered. It was carefully crystallised from dilute alcohol (1:1) as small square plates, m.p. 165-67° (decomp.). (Found: S, 11.60. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3S$ requires S, 11.94%).

Ammonium salt of (IC) was prepared and crystallised as usual in glistening needles, m.p. 213-25° (decomp.). (Found: N, 4.91. $C_{12}H_{13}O_3NS$ requires N, 4.90%). It is soluble in hot water.

S-Benzylisothiourea derivative of (IC) was prepared from the potassium salt of (IC) and crystallised from dilute alcohol in clusters of needles, m.p. 167-68° (decomp.). (Found: S, 6.25. $C_{20}H_{22}O_5N_2S_2$ requires S, 6.45%).

4-Methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxycoumarin-8-sulphonic Acid (IIC).—The oxidation was carried out in acetic acid medium, by adding hydrogen peroxide (6 c.c. of 100 vol. + 14 c.c. of water) to the suspension of the sulphinic acid (IC, 1 g.) in acetic acid (5 c.c.) with good shaking at room temperature. Sulphinic acid went into solution, within 15 minutes. It was then diluted with water (20 c.c.) and left overnight and then neutralised with NaOH solution, when sodium salt of sulphonic acid separated, the separation being facilitated by adding sodium chloride. It was filtered, washed and dried.

S-Benzylisothiourea derivative of (IIC), prepared from the above sodium salt, was crystallised from dilute alcohol in clusters of needles, m.p. 161-62°. Mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen, prepared according to Merchant and Shah (*loc. cit.*), showed no lowering.

4-Methyl-6-ethylcoumarin-8-ethylsulphone (IVC).—Potassium salt of the sulphinic acid (IC) was first dissolved in water (10 c.c.) by heating and it was then refluxed by adding alcohol (12 c.c.) and ethyl iodide (1.5 c.c.) for 16 hours. A small amount of a solid, m.p. 255° (decomp.), that separated from the boiling mixture was removed (not investigated), and the mixture was cooled when the sulphone was obtained in a pure state. It crystallised from alcohol in shining rectangular plates, m.p. 125-27°, yield 0.8 g. (Found: S, 10.37. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2S$ requires S, 10.81%).

4-Methyl-6-ethyl-7-hydroxy-8-chloromercuri-coumarin (VC) was prepared from (IC) by adding an alcoholic solution of mercuric chloride and purified as usual as shining needles. It became pasty at 270° (turned yellow at 250°). (Found: Hg, 45.81. $C_{12}H_{11}O_2ClHg$ requires Hg, 45.67%).

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